

CREATING AN INTERACTIVE EDUCATIONAL PIPELINE TO TEACH HOW TO DEVELOP AN IMAGE CLASSIFICATION A.I. FROM THE DATA ACQUISITION TO THE IMPLEMENTATION.

Bruno Gobato Simões, Dr. Arnaldo de Carvalho Junior, Dr. Walter Augusto Varella.
 IFSP – bruno.simoies@aluno.ifsp.edu.br, IFSP – varella@ifsp.edu.br, IFSP – adecarvalhojr@ifsp.edu.br.

Abstract – Due to their multiutility, image classification models have become one of the most popular Artificial Intelligence (AI) models in recent years. Additionally, the market value of AI has been exploding recently, estimated to reach \$15.7 trillion by 2030. Unfortunately, reports show that Brazil has not developed as much AI as other countries. To stimulate the development of AI, this project aims to create an educational pipeline on how to create and develop an image classification AI. In the end, a functional and interactive Pipeline was published on a website.

Keywords: Interactive Pipeline; Artificial Intelligence; AI Educational; Machine Learning; Image Classification.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence, or better known as AI, has grown a lot in popularity in recent years. A large part of it is due to its usability and easy-to-use tools, which notably attract the average internet user, who can use it for their personal or professional business. Many famous AI's such as ChatGPT, Midjourney, Bard and even the most recent Google Gemini, have taken over the internet in a way never seen before, with billions of visits per year and hundreds of millions of active users, these AI tools are not only responsible for a drastic change in the way we do many things today but also for the emergence of a new and extremely profitable area of the market [1, 2]. The number of visits and comparison of AI Tools can be seen in Table 1, as the representation of the emergence of the AI market in Fig. 1.

Table 1 – Comparison between web visits from different AI tools over the one-year spam period [1].

AI Tool	Total Web Visits (Sept 2022 to Aug 2023)
ChatGPT	14.6B
Character.AI	3.8B
QuillBot	1.1B
Midjourney	500.4M
Hugging Face	316.6M
Google Bard	241.6M

Figure 1 – Global AI Market Revenue by Year [2].

Following this trend, many companies have adopted the usage of AI tools, because they improve productivity, thus increasing the company's profit. Statistics say that over 35% of the companies worldwide have been using AI on their business, and that this number has been increasing significantly over the past few years [3].

Nowadays, AI has become synonymous with the country's development. Not investing in AI can be considered a stupid attitude in terms of government management, since it is estimated that AI could contribute up to \$15.7 trillion to the global economy by 2030, that is, more than the current economic output of both China and India combined [4].

Unfortunately, Brazil has not invested as much in AI as other countries, positioning itself in 30th position on a global ranking, which classifies countries using the following parameters: Talent, Infrastructure, Operating Environment, Research, Development, Government Strategy, Commercial, Scale and Intensity [5]. As previous stated, a country that does not invest on AI can be seen as an outdated country by foreign investors, leading to less investment and improvement in the domestic economy. A visual representation of the global rank can be seen in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 – Image representation of the AI global Rank [5].

In addition to the economic value of Artificial Intelligence, research into the development of new AI models can present an even greater value in terms of technological advancement in the country.

AI, in general, is basically an artificial neural network, made up of artificial neurons that are simply mathematical functions that simulate a real neuron [6]. Besides the neural network, the development of an AI also depends on the data and the general configuration (such as number of cycles, selected function and others). Its efficiency can be significantly changed by how you construct it, for example, simple errors in the dataset can harm the functioning of the AI [7]. A graphical representation of an artificial neuron can be seen in Fig. 3

Figure 3 – Graphic representation of an Artificial Neuron with multiple input [6].

Among the multiple types of Artificial Intelligence models, one that stands out the most is the Image Classification model, which can have multiple applications, from health to financial or governmental, and can currently be seen as one of the most used and researched [8].

To improve the development of AI in Brazil, we decided to create an Educational Pipeline that teaches how to develop an Image Classification AI, covering everything from data selection to implementation. This type of pipeline will not only be useful for people who have never developed an AI, but also for people who have developed one but have not been as successful at it, due to small common errors.

A Pipeline can be described as “a linear sequence of specialized modules used for pipelining.” by Oxford, but, at the end, the term pipeline is very flexible and can be used very differently depending on the topic, in this case, the term pipeline will be more used like a flowchart, in which the ideas and the “tutorial” will be organized in a sequential way [9].

DEVELOPMENT

Initially we had to discuss which topics should be addressed in the pipeline, for this a meeting was scheduled and an initial proposal was made. In this proposal, the following topics were defined for the pipeline: Input Data Selection, Data Processing, AI Model Selection, Tool/Platform Selection, AI Training, Results Analysis, Final Adjustments and Implementation. The board made during this meeting can be seen in Fig. 4.

The first step now was to create a document with all the text information that would be displayed in the Pipeline and its references. At the end, a document with 8 pages and roughly 2600 words was made, disregarding the references. A screenshot of this document can be seen in Fig. 5.

After finishing creating the document, some ideas were proposed on how to implement the text in some

type of Pipeline. Some of them through Hyperlinks, others through Google Slides, but as there was a lot of text involved, we wanted something very interactive and easy to read, which wouldn't tire the user so easily.

Figure 4 – Photo of the board notations taken during the meeting.

Figure 5 – Pipeline document screenshot.

So, after searching a lot for interactive pipeline creation platforms, we didn't find any and, because of that, the only solution left was to program in HTML, CSS and JavaScript, which can be a little complicated, but at the end of the day It is very customizable and meet all our needs. A photo taken during one of the programming sessions can be seen in Fig. 6.

Figure 6 – Photo taken during the development of the website.

After almost 1700 lines of code, we were able to develop an interactive Pipeline within a website, containing all topics, references and image representations. The website also has responsive resolution, that allows users to access the website in any type of device, and a button that redirects to the EAILab website (our Embedded Artificial Intelligence Laboratory website). A screenshot of the finished website can be seen on Fig. 7.

Figure 7 – Finished website screenshot.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Finishing the development of the Pipeline we had to publish it somewhere, as it was an HTML file, it could be published in hundreds of different places, but in the end, it was decided that the best place to publish this type of website was on GitHub Pages, a place commonly used to publish pages on this type of subject.

The website itself is very practical, detailed, easy to use and easy to understand, containing various buttons and image representations that can significantly help people develop their image classification AI or even improve its efficiency.

An example of how using the techniques and solutions presented in the Pipeline can affect AI efficiency can be seen in a previous article developed by one of the EAILab researchers, in which during the development of a brain tumor detection AI, changes in parameters and data processing managed to improve its AI F1-Score from 78,26% to 94,4% [10]. A picture taken during one of the tests made after the improvement can be seen in Fig. 8.

Figure 8 – The EAILab researcher testing the efficiency of the improved AI.

The website can be accessed via the EAILab GitHub page via the following link: <https://eailab-ifsp.github.io/AI-CLASSIFICATION-PIPELINE/index.html>. It is worth mentioning that the website can be automatically translated into English using the Google Chrome browser, which has an integrated translation tool.

REFERENCES

- [1] CONTE, Niccolo. “Ranked: The Most Popular AI Tools”, Visual Capitalist. 2024. (Available at: <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/ranked-the-most-popular-ai-tools/>)
- [2] OMIDIA apud HOWARD, Josh. “The AI software market's global annual revenue stands at around \$100 billion”, Exploding Topics. 2024. (Available at: <https://explodingtopics.com/blog/ai-statistics>)
- [3] MATLEENA S., NURUL S., “41 AI Statistics and Trends in 2024”, Hostinger UK. 2024. (Available at: [https://www.hostinger.co.uk/tutorials/ai-statistics#:~:text=Artificial%20intelligence%20\(AI\)%20adoption%20is,healthcare%2C%20retail%2C%20and%20manufacturing](https://www.hostinger.co.uk/tutorials/ai-statistics#:~:text=Artificial%20intelligence%20(AI)%20adoption%20is,healthcare%2C%20retail%2C%20and%20manufacturing))
- [4] PWC. “AI Analysis – Sizing the Prize”, PWC Network. 2020. (Available: <https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/issues/analytics/assets/pwc-ai-analysis-sizing-the-prize-report.pdf>)
- [5] CESAREO, Serena et al. “The Global AI Index 2024”, Tortoise Media. 2024. (Available at: <https://www.tortoisemedia.com/intelligence/global-ai/>)
- [6] A. de Carvalho, J. F. Justo, B. A. Angélico, A. M. de Oliveira and J. I. da Silva Filho, "Rotary Inverted Pendulum Identification for Control by Paraconsistent Neural Network," in IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 74155-74167, 2021.
- [7] DE SILVA, Daswin et al. Patterns, Volume 3, Issue 6, 100489
- [8] M. Sornam, K. Muthusubash and V. Vanitha, "A Survey on Image Classification and Activity Recognition using Deep Convolutional Neural Network Architecture," 2017 Ninth International Conference on Advanced Computing (ICoAC), Chennai, India, 2017, pp. 121-126, doi: 10.1109/ICoAC.2017.8441512.
- [9] Oxford Languages. Oxford University Press, 2024.
- [10] SIMÕES, Bruno Gobato et al. SPECIALIZED BRAIN TUMOR DETECTION SYSTEM FOR SUPERIOR VIEW OF CRANIAL MRI USING AI AND TINY ML TECHNIQUES. In: Anais Do Workshop De Micro-ondas. Clube de Autores, 2023. p. 107.